

Tartari, Morena

University of Antwerp, Belgium

«*If we don't split her equally*». *Reading contemporary family struggles through Bourdieu*

1. Introduction

The actors involved in the family as a field (Bourdieu 1996)—that is, parents, children, and relatives involved in various capacities—experience moments of rupture and crisis. This article aims to examine some aspects of the family crisis by applying some conceptual tools of Pierre Bourdieu's sociological theory to the results of a transnational study, with the purpose of showing how these tools facilitate the explanation of this moment of crisis in the contemporary family. I specifically use the terms *crisis* or *disruption* in this paper to refer to the separation and divorce of parental couples with minor children. These situations of change have different impacts on the life trajectories of agents (Nieuwenhuis, Maldonado 2018), in relation to their capital and their habitus. The empirical research presented has taken into consideration the experience of mothers who have become *single* after a separation or divorce, focusing in particular on situations where an element of disruption is constituted by the ex-spouse's violence and without neglecting the influence of the other fields on that of the family. These relational ruptures cause a series of crises or ruptures on social, economic, and biographical levels, highlighting the implications and collusion of mothers with the field to which they belong.

Bourdieu's (1996) work allows the conceiving of the family *as a field* characterized by both reproduction and change. Family, like other fields, comprises dominant and dominated sections and an orthodox definition of reality that contends against heterodox definitions (Bourdieu 1977).

Taking into account conflicts of interest, relations of power, and struggles that concern boundaries

and membership, Atkinson (2016) then extends this vision of the family and indicates unexplored pathways for research.

The research project follows Atkinson's invitation to add an empirical contribution to theoretically refining the idea of the family as a field of struggle. The evidence from this study shows that Bourdieu's work is not only concerned with reproduction (Jenkins 1982; 2014), but it also promotes the analysis of processes of change and transformation (Fowler 2020).

The path I propose in this article is as follows: I critically introduce the concepts of Pierre Bourdieu's social theory concerning family as a field through a review of them, accompanied by some recent studies that have used them. I then focus on the concepts used to inductively interpret the results that emerged from my research. I continue by presenting the methodology of the study—Institutional Ethnography (IE) (Smith 2005), outlining the role that Bourdieu and Smith's approach played in conducting the research. I then discuss the results of the study by showing how elements emerging from rupture and crisis can be interpreted through Bourdieu's conceptual tools. Finally, I conclude by proposing an examination of the salient aspects that emerged and of the desirable future empirical contributions.

2. Family as a field

Bourdieu's approach has received limited attention with regard to its potential in analyzing the family and its crisis. Erroneously, Bourdieu has been accused of being a reproductive theorist and of giving the family attention only as a conductor of the transmission of capital (Morgan 1999, 21). On the contrary, his social theory grasps the power structures to which the family field is interconnected and its role not only in reproduction but also in the fractures of this social and cultural reproduction (Atkinson 2014, 45).

Bourdieu (1990a; 1990b) initially defined the family in terms of «practical kinship» or «the field of relationships that are constantly re-used», and which are not unrelated to conflicts of interest,

resistances, tensions, and struggles over membership and boundaries. Bourdieu allows the distinction between official and practical kinship, between the rules of the game and how the game is played by the actors (Morgan 2011).

Subsequently, Bourdieu (1996) returned to the definitional question of the family, explaining that the family, as understood in the common sense is something recently invented and destined not to remain so. Alternatively, for Bourdieu (*ibidem*, 20), the family is a *reified* category, a collective principle of the construction of collective reality, which assumes its implicit descriptions and prescriptions—a *nomos*—that is learned through socialization. The family is therefore a principle rooted in the objectivity of social structures and in the subjectivity of mental structures, so much so that it appears natural.

The structures of the family, such as kinship and social bodies, can only be perpetuated thanks to the symbolic and practical daily work of creating and maintaining the family feeling—the disposition to love, cohesion, and work—that often falls on the woman on the basis of the organization of tasks based on gender roles (*ibidem*, 22). The daily practices of family members are subject to the structure of power relations within the field in which male domination plays a predominant role. The family is one of the key sites of accumulation and intergenerational transmission of social, cultural, and economic capital. Being in conformity with the legitimate definition of family is a symbolic and *de facto* privilege.

Bourdieu does not fail to underline how, in the work of categorizing the family and its members, the State plays a fundamental role by favoring certain types of family organization and helping to reproduce the legitimacy of families that correspond to certain indicators of conformity, through the institutional discourses that circulate in the common sense.

Atkinson (2016) explains the importance of Bourdieu for family studies. Atkinson's work presents the potential of Bourdiesian concepts to explain the crises and struggles of individuals who belong to the field of the contemporary family (Atkinson 2014, 224). Atkinson's contribution consists of developing the discussion concerning the constitutive elements of the family as a field: its *doxa*, its

internal struggles with respect to capital, its borders, and its roots in a larger universe of family relationships. First, Atkinson makes it possible to place the family as a field in relation to other national and international fields of power (political, bureaucratic, economic, religious, intellectual, media, legal, scientific, etc.), which contribute to providing a legitimate definition of reality, causing a tension between orthodox and heterodox definitions of reality (Bourdieu 1977).

Such definitions of the family are dominated by the prevailing orthodox perspective offered by the Western world, which sees the family as the fundamental natural unit of society based on traditional gender roles (Atkinson 2014, 225). Within the family field, Atkinson identifies a struggle for an orthodox definition between the richest factions in terms of cultural capital (e.g., experts, therapists, and teachers) and the richest factions in terms of economic capital. The heterodox version is instead supported by a radical faction (Bourdieu 2001) that advocates non-consanguinity, non-heterosexuality, and non-nuclear definitions of family.

Atkinson identifies a dialectical relationship between material conditions and representations. This dialogue allows for reshaping the doxa and, therefore, continually questioning the definitions.

Rooted in the shared experience of family members, there is also a family-specific doxa influenced by available capital, gendered dispositions, as well as expectations and anticipations—particularly those regarding the future of each member (Bourdieu, Passeron 1979, 12; Bourdieu 1990, 54).

Finally, Atkinson highlights a fundamental aspect of the family: conflict. Since the members possess different capitals, even symbolic ones, the family field consists of a system of objective and structural relations of domination (Bourdieu 1998, 68–70).

Each member also has power and capitals from other fields that affect the distribution of symbolic capital within the family (an example of this is male domination within the family, with its most manifest expression in domestic violence). Family trajectories also play a role in determining the structure and struggles of particular family fields, such as when new members forcibly enter (Atkinson 2014, 229). Furthermore, in family fields, where the family doxa is strenuously defended and affirmed by parents who manage to have a united front, the struggles are reduced, and the final

result is a reproduction of the social position. However, in fields where this does not happen and where orthodoxy and heterodoxy come into conflict, there can be ambivalence or rejection of the inheritance, thus generating trajectories and practices that deviate from the family doxa and generate a break with it. A classic example is that of parents' expectations in school that are not met by their children (Bourdieu 1999; Bourdieu 2000).

These threats to the family doxa become concrete when the boundaries of the family field are threatened or changed. For example, an absent father may not be perceived as playing a role in the field (Atkinson 2014, 230), and members of step-families may be accepted or not accepted as members of the new *real* family—resulting in objective structures coming into conflict with subjective perceptions, which can have concrete effects on dispositions and family doxa through practices.

Although he does not take them into consideration, separation or divorce can be categorized among the events that Atkinson (2021) indicates as *a fall from grace*. Disgraces are the product of intra-or extra-field dynamics and struggles. The violation of the rules of the game that the author quotes in the definition suits the intra-field logic of the family field well. Furthermore, negative social capital is generated by *dis-grace*. This can be the case for men accused of domestic violence and people with many family breakdowns.

The literature that has devoted space to the application of Bourdieu's conceptual tools to family crises is scant. Studies related to one of the fields often linked to the family crisis, the legal one, are rare (e.g., Hacker 2008).

3. Conceptual tools to interpret family crises

As Pitzalis (2019, 30) suggests, Bourdieu is a sociologist of crises since «his analyzes concern the moments in which a crisis of the habitus (*hysteresis*) occurs in conjunction with structural transformations of the social space and of the different fields in which it is articulated in

contemporary societies». Therefore, among the tools proposed by Bourdieu, that of *hysteresis* is a fundamental concept to analyze systemic change (Hardy 2014, 144). In family disruptions, the organizing forces of the family field change, the aspects of everyday life in which practical kinship is exercised are missing, a sort of disruption is generated between field and habitus «in particular, when a field undergoes a major crisis and its regularities (even its rules) are profoundly changed» (Bourdieu 2000, 160).

Hysteresis represents «a mismatch between two elements which were previously coordinated» and «the possibility of change which is permanent and irreversible» (Hardy 2014, 128). Field and habitus are conceived as dependent elements, and hysteresis happens where and when habitus fails in its attempt to act in line with the field in which it usually operates, it therefore finds itself disconnected from the field in which assumptions change, and nothing can be taken for granted anymore (Bourdieu, 1990a). This new condition generated by the lack of synchrony between habitus and the positions available in the field brings with it opportunities and risks (Bourdieu, 2015). Only agents who have privileged positions—a favorable combination of capitals—will be able to easily overcome the crisis, seize the opportunities, and reduce the risks of a changing trajectory. Where then the habitus assumes a practical awareness of the potential of the situation, it allows the agent to manipulate the situation to his own advantage (Cronin 1996, 65). In addition to those of Bourdieu (2002; 1988; 1999), other studies have used the concept of *hysteresis* (e.g., Strand, Lizardo 2017; Graham 2020). It enables us to detect crises within a field or between different fields. However, its application to the family field is only hinted at.

Another conceptual tool to be taken into consideration in the analysis of crises in the family field is *co-implication* or *collusion* with the field (Pitzalis 2019). Assuming that habitus allows the production of practices that are able to adapt to the social order that produces them, an active co-implication of the agent in the social space follows, also described by Bourdieu as *forced collusion* with the group to which they belong. This explanation, applicable to different fields, capacitates us to understand the functioning of the relationship between habitus and the family field.

Habitus has the practical experience of the group, its doing, and its being to the point of incorporating its rules without questioning them. It is, therefore, the fruit and foundation of a complicity—integration into a certain social space and the sharing of a certain doxa—or of an implicit collusion (*ibidem*, 40) between all members of the field. Co-implication in the field is therefore a form of solidarity with the field itself and of conversion to the dominant logic of the field. In this game of forces, agents—even when they try to change the organization of the field and its rules—can end up reproducing its structural logic due to the internalized dispositions that guide their actions (*ibidem*). The logic of the field therefore does not cease during conflicts; on the contrary, they are reconfirmed by them.

The accomplice contenders (Bourdieu 1984, 149) may be the dominated and may not be able to put into practice rules other than those already learned within the field, thus failing to subvert the order. An example of a figure of complicity (Pitzalis 2019, 39-40) is that of the dominated woman, which has sparked heated debate in feminist literature (e.g., Butler 1999; Lovell 2000) since Bourdieu describes the dominated woman as an accomplice of male domination. However, this co-implication or collusion should not be understood in a moral sense but merely in a descriptive one. The complicity between field and habitus is produced within the family field by socializing moral, cultural, and linguistic rules. The circular processes of the naturalization of subordination are relational processes of assimilating the rules of the game and its stakes and incorporating provisions that contribute to the construction of a habitus. They are understood as devices of symbolic violence (Bourdieu 2001).

In the relational dialectical process between continuity and change in the field, forms of resistance also emerge. The concept of *resistance* has received great attention in recent years to define a specific field of *resistance studies* (e.g., Polese, Murru 2020). However, the meaning of resistance in Bourdieu's theory differs slightly from interactionist stances. The forms of resistance are not fractures with respect to the logic of the field but are «forms of commitment» and of «implication» that take place within a given field and that can contribute to accelerating its transformation and

modifying its relations of strength or resources (Pitzalis 2019, 31). The forms of opposition that we understand as forms of resistance are therefore part of what Bourdieu (2005) defines *illusio*, or an adherence to the very logics of the field, without which there would be no legitimacy, even for the agents who oppose its logic—who guarantee their existence thanks to their co-implication.

Although this interpretation of the forms of resistance may appear counterintuitive, it helps us detect how much the field can imprison its agents, whose power relations and whose struggle for resources may appear meaningless to those outside those specific power relationships.

Empirical research that applies a Bourdieusian reading to these forms of everyday resistance is scant. Casey's study (2021) on single mothers and acts of resistance against the welfare-to-work policy describes the everyday forms of resistance of single mothers against symbolic violence and domination and their efforts in converting individual forms of resistance into collective action.

Casey observes that action in the field is limited by the resources available to agents and the extent of the recognition afforded to them. It therefore seems that the concept of resistance in relation to Bourdieu's field theory should be critically problematized.

4. Investigating field fractures: the research study

The results discussed in this article are taken from the study STRESS-Mums (see Tartari 2019), a mixed-method study conducted using the approach of IE established by Smith (2005). Considered an alternative sociology, IE is both a theory and a method and has the ability to explicate tensions of the social organization of knowledge, describing how and why they are organized invisibly by conceptual practices of power that regulate what people know and do in everyday life.

The study sought to understand how institutions—in particular the judiciary one—rule the mothers' everyday lives during the journey of separation or divorce, from a double-parent family to a single-parent family, with different nuances in custody arrangements and family trajectories. The study was conducted in four European countries through 50 in-depth interviews with lone mothers and

professionals belonging to the judiciary field, analysis of documents from civil proceedings and from multidisciplinary professionals' conferences, and photo-voice activities with single mothers. In particular, mothers were involved in two rounds of interviews: the first, an in-depth interview that explored how institutions ruled their experience and trajectory and which forms of resistance they enacted; the second, an in-depth interview that questioned the documents (e.g., legal petitions) that ruled their experience of separation or divorce more thoroughly.

The choice to involve only mothers is given by their historical position of subordination within the family field (Bimbi 1997; Bimbi 2000), which has also been highlighted in Italy in recent years, and also due to the policies and legislative changes introduced in 2006 (Bimbi, Trifiletti 2006).

Sampling took into account mothers' class, gender, and ethnicity to investigate how experiences and practices differ in relation to different mothers' habitus. The participants' recruitment criteria were discussed at the beginning of the project with professionals from the judicial field. Mothers who filed a request for exclusive custody of their children to the court were recruited. Professionals working in the same courts where the mothers had initiated and concluded the separation procedure were selected. Participants were overtly informed about the aims of the study. The study received ethical approval before its start.

On a methodological and ethical level, the truthfulness of the accounts collected by the interviewees regarding episodes of violence or family dynamics and relations with institutions was not questioned. Many had former partners with final judgments of Intimate Partner Violence (IPV). It was possible to find confirmation from the documentation provided by them and from the narratives of the interviewees themselves. The collected data were analyzed by thematic maps.

Dorothy Smith's sociological approach, like Bourdieu's, can be considered a form of theoretically founded inductivism (Pitzalis 2010). In fact, like Smith, Bourdieu believes that theoretical and conceptual issues must be taken into consideration as scientific knowledge tools to answer the complex issues raised by empirical research and to explain such empirical results. Therefore, the IE approach allows for interpretations with different conceptual tools from those of the IE itself.

Inspired by ethnomethodology and Marxian materialism, Smith's alternative sociology was established and developed in a reflexive feminist context. It investigates the ruling relations, starting from participants' standpoints (often women or other dominated social categories), how texts (e.g., law) affect everyday practices and discourses, and how they reproduce institutional discourses. There are some elements of resonance between IE and Bourdieu's approach to social research. For instance, IE utilizes maps to describe the effects of ruling relations on participants' journeys within and through institutions; Bourdieu aims to map out the objective structures of the field in terms of the form of power present to analyze the positions of actors in the field relative to the power relations of the field and to analyze the habitus of the actors to identify the way in which their action is limited by the power relations of the field (Grenfell 2014, 73). However, IE diverges from the use of metaphors and language, with which Bourdieu describes the social world through his theory (Smith 2005, 184–85).

In this article, the results of my study are interpreted through some Bourdiesian concepts; instead, the discussion based on the interpretative elements made available by the IE is omitted, which, having a specific lexicon, would need a separate essay. These results offer me the opportunity to critically discuss Bourdieu's conceptual tools. In the discussion of the results, only accounts from Italian, Belgian, and Spanish fieldwork are used, as these countries have similar socio-cultural aspects with respect to the discourse relating to the family and the legal changes that concern it, unlike the fieldwork conducted in the UK.

5. Findings: family field's crises from mothers' standpoints

The mothers involved in the research project reported various problems congruent with the descriptions that the literature provides with respect to mothers who manage family life after a family disruption alone (e.g., Bernardi, Mortelmans 2018). For all of them, separation, regardless of the causes (betrayal or domestic violence), meant entering a phase of *dis-grace* (Atkinson 2021)

from which they emerged with paths that sometimes lasted several years after the dispersion of many forms of capital accumulated during the marriage. The state of disgrace generated by divorce or separation brought them to a downward trend in social mobility, and this is coherent with the data that the literature usually shows for women (Grella 1990; Nieuwenhuis, Maldonado 2018; Thielemans, Mortelmans 2021).

Often, this change in the family field generates *negative* social capital for women who previously relied on the social capital of their partners. Many of them have entered for more or less long periods in a phase of more or less acute social or economic suffering and have had to seek help and support in social welfare.

In this discussion, I consider three fundamental aspects of the crisis that characterize the experience of these mothers in the path of separation, interpreted through three Bourdiesian notions: hysteresis, collusion, and resistance.

Out of time and place or about hysteresis

Separations of partners can generate exceedingly noticeable changes between the previous and subsequent conditions, or they can occur without excessively changing the family field. As long as all the actors continue to collaborate even after the separation—acting *as if*—the field does not undergo excessive changes in the relations between the forces that compose it. This is not the case with *hysteresis*.

The changes in which hysteresis occurs are sudden—non-gradual—changes in which the discrepancies become relevant; there is a sense of being *out of time and place*, a failure to adapt to how circumstances are changing. The ways in which the habitus will evolve are unpredictable, and the positioning of the individual in the field is indeterminate (Hardy 2014, 127). The displacement between habitus and field has an effect on the structure of the field itself (*ibidem*). This was the case for all the interviewees who, to varying degrees and nuances, experienced these discrepancies. The

misalignment between habitus and field sometimes becomes traumatic for parents and children. A substantially frequent situation is that of a fracture that generates economic suffering in the newly established family unit of the mother and children. Significant in this regard is the testimony of Y., a Spanish artist who, following the breakup of the relationship by her partner, who was the father of her two children, found herself involved in various civil and criminal proceedings and in serious economic difficulties.

The first months after the separation, he was present with the children, but the moment the other person [the new partner] appeared, the problems started. She wanted to take on the role of mother for my children. I started to protest, and things got complicated and suddenly. The father stopped paying the agreed maintenance. I was at home with two very young children; at that time, I worked very sporadically. [...] Financially, it was tremendous. The bank made me a loan of 25 thousand euros, which I am still paying. With the loan, I managed to survive, to support myself for a year and a half. You can imagine the trauma in that moment. He wanted custody of the children. That's where the *judicial war* unilaterally started because I didn't want to. It was very traumatic. It has been, I think, five long years of a lot of fear. I felt very lonely and very attached because the father's economic power is very high, not like mine. [...] I thought that, with the fact that he was powerful, I couldn't do anything about it. My son was totally dominated by his father and did not want to see me—my daughter almost the same. It was very very difficult, very painful. Then, in the end, after all the judicial process, to my surprise [the court] didn't agree with him. They wrote that as a father he is very authoritarian, that he does not like to be contradicted, [and] that he is a manipulative person.

[Spanish fieldwork, Interview n. 8]

The symbolic violence exercised against Y. concerns the areas of her life in which she has less capital than her ex-partner: the economic, social, and emotional spheres.

He is a famous artist and has come to influence my work. After the separation, I no longer worked as an artist. Look at what his influence has been in this regard, not only a sexist violence on his part, but also a social violence. [Spanish fieldwork, Interview n. 8]

However, not all interviewees are as aware as Y. of the violence they suffer and of the adaptation strategies they can implement after the fracture to realign habitus and field. Women appear as agents trained in specific socialization processes in which practices and discourses have been incorporated into the habitus that do not permit them to leave the relationship with the dominant and to restructure it.

One of the leitmotifs of the interviews collected was the lack of recognition by the court of the influence that the partner had on life and career choices during the marriage. During their marriage, many of the interviewees had given up a job to look after their families and children, adjusting to adhering to an orthodox role and accepting living with an evident inequality of economic capital compared to the husband.

At the time of separation, the former partner often tries to obtain shared custody with the arrangement of children at 50% of the time and expenses, even if he had never previously looked after the children. This allows him to avoid paying a maintenance allowance to the mother. When the judicial field professionals comment that the 50% division is in favor of mother who can work, mother instead feels victim of symbolic violence, as she is not recognized for the difficulties that she will encounter in entering the world of work after years of not being involved in it. Her full-time commitment within the family in previous years and the fact that this was often a choice imposed by the partner who had greater economic and symbolic capital is also not taken into account. Here is an excerpt from G.'s interview, whose experience is common to many others.

[...] he just wants 50/50 Because the children are 50% from him and 50% from me. That's how he sees this. Everything has to be divided exactly in the middle. That's how he sees it. And I don't agree

with that because before the divorce, I spent more time with children than he did. He was very active in sports activities and stuff like that. So, I did most of the education [and] the care of the children, and I think it should just keep going like that because he made the decision to go and [these] are the consequences. [Belgian fieldwork, Interview n. 2]

This is often the moment in which women who feel that they have cooperated for years in keeping the family field in balance feel that the institutions do not recognize their due in symbolic and material terms. The difficulty of accepting change concerns not only symbolic and economic aspects but also social and time-management aspects in relation to children.

Because it's not very enjoyable when there is a party within the family and I have to be there without the children because it's like; yeah, it's [a] party but I'm alone. That's difficult. But on my side of the family, they just change the dates. [...] Maybe another example, indeed is the birthdays of the children. Now I had [a] blessing that her birthday was on a Sunday and it was a Sunday of the change so I saw her at 5:00 o'clock in the evening because I know it will be very very difficult when I am not with them on their birthday. So that was fortunate because, yeah, you miss a lot of moments. [Belgian fieldwork, Interview n. 2]

Hysteresis brings threats to far more serious consequences for children, who in turn experience the breaking of the field and the misalignment of their habitus. Parents represent their children as «heirs» (Pitzalis 2019, 33), but the changes in separation undermine the investment and expectations of parents. The trajectory prefigured for the heir and supported by the family as a collective enterprise is undermined by the separation. After the separation, in fact, the heir will no longer have the same social, cultural, economic, and symbolic capital. Although seldom explicit in sociological literature, this issue is often the fulcrum of many conflicting separations. The family is no longer a unit that guarantees expected reproduction, and each of the parents can start a struggle to align the child's trajectory with their own expectations in competition with the other parent.

There is, therefore, again a mismatch with respect to the starting conditions, the expectations of the members, and the reality of the field.

Sometimes, in an attempt to preserve the force field unaltered and to prevent alterations in the habitus from altering the reproductive mechanism, parents seek collaboration and continuity as parents even when they are no longer a couple. However, this is not always possible. As with school failures (*ibidem*, 34), divorce is also a «source of frustration and split», since it produces ambivalent habituses, which question family field's uniqueness and the consistency of members' identity and trajectory.

The imagined heir can therefore no longer be such an heir and this colludes with the fears and anxieties of parents about risks and appropriate parenting practices (Beck, Beck-Gernsheim 1995). The fears regarding the trajectories of the heir clearly emerge from the story of L., a young woman who conceived a daughter with her partner, who left home a few months after the birth of their daughter. The cohabitant did not pay support for the daughter, found another partner, and showed no interest in having contact with the daughter. However, L. was distressed that the absence of the father figure could damage her daughter psychologically and relied on the advice of a popular psychological book.

The title of the book is something like «A week to mom and a week to dad. What children really need in a divorce». I was really thinking: «We need to do it 50/50 because that will be good for our daughter. If we don't split it equally, she will turn into a monster or something else». [...] *I felt so guilty for my daughter!*

Note by the interviewer: Later, in another part of the interview, the mother began to cry and she explained to me that, as she has not been able to ensure a 50/50 real agreement; every day she is worried about the psychological wellbeing of her daughter. [Belgian fieldwork, interview n. 8]

L.'s account is an example of the fear that the heir will become *defective* as a result of mothers' behavior. The compromise implemented is to come to terms with the judicial/intellectual field and an abusive former partner rather than risk the heir being compromised. Transmitting an inheritance (social, cultural, economic, emotional, symbolic) requires adherence to a model and a project in a coherent and cooperative way, since if already in normal conditions the family project for the heir is in danger, after separation it is even more so. The requests for children's allowances by the mothers always aim to fill in the gap between expected and real trajectories for the heir.

In the next section, we observe how L. colludes with the field in an attempt to preserve some of its logic, including protecting the imagined trajectory of the heir.

The ambivalence of complicity, the cost of conversion

Each parent has learned the rules of functioning in their own family field and does not question them as tacit and shared knowledge. It is in solidarity with the field that they integrate into a family social space and share a *doxa*. After separation, these forms of co-implication with the field can at least partially disappear. However, agents have an interest in the survival and continuity of the field, so co-implication as a form of solidarity and collusion in accepting the dominant rules does not cease. Parents can show a form of engagement with the field, even in the face of the crisis, precisely to ensure continuity in the field and protect the reproduction of the resources intended for the heir. When continuing to be accomplices in the rules of the field means accepting its dominant logic to the detriment of one's own interests, we are faced with forms of *collusion*.

A classic example of collusion with the field is given by the case of L., introduced above. L. did not agree to telling friends and acquaintances that the partner was gone and kept the separation hidden for a long time. The family of origin supported her in the legal action she took against her former partner, who previously also refused family mediation. Her complicity with the field and the acceptance of the logic that indicated as indisputable symbolic capital, in particular that of the father

figure, was so high that she failed to grasp either the opportunities for resistance and those of change or the strategies of the former partner to maintain the forces of the field in his favor. Only the lawyer tried to show her the effects of collusion with the logic of the family field and with the ways of power relations imposed by the former partner.

But [the lawyer] suggested to me to read [in-depth] that book for *other* insights about *co-parenting*, that it doesn't have to be 50/50 in every situation. [...] And [at the court hearing], he [the ex-partner] wanted a 50/50 agreement on paper. On paper! And then, [after the hearing] he said: «I will show up whenever I feel like it». I didn't realized it immediately because I was focused on the calendars. But when we left, my lawyer said: «Wow, it's so crazy of him to say that to the judge, to ask 50/50, because then he would also get 50% of the child allowance». [Belgian fieldwork; Interview n. 8]

Despite the former partner's lack of interest in the relationship with his daughter and the failure to pay the maintenance, L. does not accept being alone in raising her daughter to not lose the symbolic capital of the father figure. Indeed, she is so focused on the practical aspects—the *calendars*—that are part of her previously internalized practical disposition within the field that she does not even notice the many facets and possibilities of co-parenting and the strategies of the former partner. Collusion with the logic of the field after its crisis has costs and opens the way to various situations of symbolic violence. One of the most emotionally complex interviews was with B., mother of three children, and wife of a peer who physically and psychologically mistreated her and their minor children for many years up to forced removal and who carried out several assassination attempts aimed at the wife.

B.'s story offers an example of the cost of colluding and converting to field logic when they change and when symbolic and material violence becomes more worrying. However, she also takes into account a form of resistance to the influence of fields outside the family, which would have suggested that she file a complaint long ago. Inserted in a patriarchal culture, not employed for

years by the choice of her husband—who preferred her to take care of their children—B. did not take into consideration the idea of separation even after years of violence. She resisted external demands from other fields, but in fact, her collusion with the family field was so profound that it prevented her from escaping to safety.

The last 15 days I have seen death... We were at home [on vacation] and therefore he [my husband] had more chances of attacking us... so I would take the children and take them out of the house to keep them away from him... But he had already planned our end... [...] The Carabinieri [police officer] who listened to my story told me, «If you don't report it, I have to do it for a matter of responsibility, because there are minors involved». [...] At that point, I said, «I'll do it, because I have to be the one to protect my children and he is not». But I [didn't go] there to file a complaint, but to figure out what to do. At that moment, *I was no longer*. [From then on I canceled myself!] I only made it to protect my children... I was alone, scorched earth around... [...] I was a fly inside its web and I could do nothing but wait for the spider to come and eat me. I had no awareness of what would happen next, I'm telling the truth. [...] [she is moved] I had no idea what would have happened... I did it only for my children... *If I had been alone [without my children], he would have quietly killed me...* Instead: only the mother is left and she managed to rescue her children... damaged, wounded, with stumps... but in safety... [Italian fieldwork, Interview n. 2]

What B. explained is that if it had not been to save her children (with physical and psychological severe wounds), she—to remain within the family field—would never have made the choice to break with the field through an explicit and direct act, such as a report to the police. This collusion was also supported by his parents, to whom she had never had the strength to *confess* that she was the victim of violence because, as she also explained in a later passage of the interview, their *family spirit* would not have allowed them to understand the situation in which she lived.

B.'s story enables us to understand how the logic of the field does not cease during conflicts but is instead confirmed by them. B. and her husband continued to struggle to impose a definition of the

family field. The interference of the legal field in this case worked in the direction of breaking the collusion, ending the violence, and imposing new balances.

The conversion of B. to the judicial field logic—strongly collusive with the logic of the family field—has, for her, a greatly high cost, so high as to compel her to admit that she had to *cancel* herself to submit herself to it, with the sole purpose of protecting her children. The non-acceptance of the explanation of co-implication as an element of domestic violence is at the center of feminist criticisms directed at Bourdieu's social theory (Butler 1999).

Sometimes, the collusion with the family field is strengthened from the outside, as in the case of T., a mother who has suffered physical abuse and death threats even in front of her minor children by her husband, who for some time, even while living together, did not support his children and was under investigation for other crimes outside those concerning the family sphere.

The Carabinieri [police officers] and my lawyer put a great deal of psychological pressure on me to withdraw the two complaints I had made because he did not support economically the children... One day, on the phone, the lawyer yelled at me: «If you don't withdraw the complaints, the social workers will arrive and take your children away from you...». He and the Carabinieri thought that I was exaggerating, that I had not suffered violence. [...] Later, I changed [my] lawyer and everything changed in the trial. [Italian fieldwork, Interview n. 4]

T.'s story, like many other accounts, shows how institutions support the reproduction of the logic of the orthodox family definition at two levels: that of the specific family field—and that of the field of power that crosses the legal field—the economic field and the intellectual field, through institutionally legitimated forms of classification. These forms of classification are aimed at guaranteeing a social order through the regulation of the family in an orthodox sense, even after the rupture of the separation, and exert symbolic violence against those who deviate from or reject such forms of classification. During the evaluation, T. was threatened by the court-appointed expert to «take the children away» if she did not accept some visiting hours imposed by the ex-partner

without allowing her to negotiate. This symbolic violence against T. can only be exercised with the complicity of the dominant and the dominated.

Resistance, desistance

I have already presented the characteristics of resistance in the Bourdesian approach, different from that understood in other theoretical areas. Here, I present a fragment from K.'s interview, a young woman with two young children.

Single mothers need models, need positive inspiration. But also fathers and men need models, inspiration. We as women live in a Disney world. My mother was very sweet... rainbows everywhere... in a word: Disney world! And my brother was very I, like me. I see this also in the students that I have, they are naive. [...] It is our culture that represents mothers, but also men and women, in this way. Empowering mums is very important, explaining to them that they can do all by themselves, alone. The *Disney culture* teaches them they have to be married and be in a couple for raising children. But society can support them and they can do it alone. I have a stipend and it is enough for me and my children. It is not true that you as a single mother will stay alone for the rest of your life! [...] If you lose you virginity after that you will be able to find other men, it is not a problem. [...] If you lose your husband but you are alone, and you are not a virgin, it is not a problem, you have many other qualities, many other things that you are able to do. [Belgian fieldwork, Interview n. 9]

K. asked for starting a separation process after her husband's betrayal and a substantial lack of financial support from him for their children. When she immigrated to Belgium from an African country during her childhood, she studied and developed a profession that allowed her to become economically independent to support her children. However, she has faced years of legal proceedings in an attempt to impose rules on her husband for dealing with their children and for the

payment of allowances. Instead, the ex-husband tried to maintain his (economic and symbolic) power over her and their children by imposing informal and unregulated management.

Despite K.'s reflections on a cultural and social revolution that shows the forms of family heterodoxy starting from the family field of origin, K.'s choice to keep the legal conflict with her husband regarding maintenance and visitation rules showed his complicity with the orthodox family field. K.'s accounts are an example of what Bourdieu understands as forms of resistance and opposition—part of what Bourdieu defines as *illusion*. There is an adherence to the very logic of the field, attested by the long legal controversy that she supported, her co-implication, and her attempt to transform and modify the power relations of the field from within the field itself, as well as through an education of the children different from the one she received, which can be legitimized and become truly subversive only if imparted within the logic of the field itself (Bourdieu 1990a, 141). It is a complicity with the field that gives rise to a «permanent revolution» (Bourdieu 1994, 77), an innovation within the possibilities of the family field.

The case of N., a woman who immigrated to Belgium from an African country many years before the birth of her daughter, raises many challenging questions about how to consider the concept of resistance. Growing up in a traditional family but immigrating alone and without any network in Belgium, N. decided not to have her daughter legally recognized by her alcoholic boyfriend—who had moved away during her pregnancy. However, N. maintained constant relations between her daughter and her ex-partner without making any financial requests to him. This allowed her not to have a lawyer, court, or social services involved. N.'s choice appears heterodox in the beginning and appears as a form of *desistance* with respect to accepting the rules of the family field imposed by society: officially the father is not known to the authorities, and in this way she removed control of the legal field on the family field. Simultaneously, she constituted a family field with assumptions different from the orthodox ones, in which she not only has never experienced hysteresis but is able to maintain power over the situation.

I have never been to court or had contact with lawyers concerning my daughter [8 year old]. The Belgian government does not officially know the father as her father; my daughter is registered with my last name. [...] I bought her, her own phone and *I try not to speak badly of her father*. When she asks me why he will not come over, I tell her that he is always at work. Now she has her own phone, she contacts her father herself. [Belgian fieldwork, Interview n. 1]

However, when N. described her behavior as not unlike that of other separated mothers, looking for forms of communication with the ex-partner, even if their romantic relationship have long since ended, the implication in the family field appears present and facilitates her actions to be seen as a form of resistance to the field with which she eventually colluded through forms of informal co-parenting with the ex-partner.

N.'s interview, which ended up in the research sample by mistake (due to a misunderstanding of one of my research assistants), proved to be extremely useful in challenging us about how even the research itself has reproduced the logic of the family field, since the decision of the recruitment criteria was based on discussions with parents and experts in the legal field and, therefore, reproduced their representations.

In the solitude of mothers like N., there is a break with the orthodoxy of family fields and other fields, a being self-sufficient that seems to be affected by the need for individuality to emerge (Beck, Beck-Gernsheim 2001; Touraine 2005), but conversely, some practices and discourses that represent an orthodox vision of relationships in the family field also seem to permeate the habitus of single mothers.

Therefore, a critical question arises with respect to the usefulness of introducing binomial *resistance—desistence* in the studies of relationships in the field. The term *desistence*, borrowed from the sociology of deviance (Graham, McNeill 2017), could instead account for those forms of extreme rupture in which individuals choose not to be involved in the field and opt for forms of radical heterodoxy.

6. Conclusion

In European countries, lone parents are considered a social problem addressed by a flourishing literature (Nieuwenhuis, Maldonado 2018; Nieuwenhuis 2020). However, literature concerning the everyday life of these parents—such as the social and cultural processes that affect their lives before, during, and after separation—is still scant. Bourdieu's social theory can help in analyzing some processes that characterize lone parents' experiences within the family field microcosm and the influence of other fields.

The change introduced by the law on shared custody reflects a discourse of the intellectual field in the legal field, supported by some currents of developmental psychology and the movements of separated parents. Some scholars (Bimbi, Trifiletti 2006) have expressed concern over the introduction of a law that did not properly consider the power relations in the family field that saw women in a situation of subordination, with lower economic and cultural capital than men. The introduction of shared custody by default has changed the practices and discourses surrounding the family crisis. However, the mainstream discourse on gender equality seems to have scotomized the dynamics of power relations within the family field, imposing a reorganization that the family field cannot always incorporate.

This article highlights the validity of the Bourdiesian tools in analyzing the structural crises of the family field. The aspects that emerged from my research help us outline the conflicts within the field, the adaptations of agents to these changes, the elements that persist after disruption and crisis, the costs they entail for mothers, and how—and to what extent—the transformative actions of the field are possible.

Importantly, in all three countries considered in this analysis, mothers seem to encounter difficulties in organizing forms of collective engagement to claim specific rights for their condition.

Sometimes, they are subjects of forms of empowerment organized by institutions that define them

as fragile subjects, but even if this experience seems to offer them the input to reorganize their lives by mending the tear of the hysteresis, it does not seem to offer them the input to become organized in advocacy actions to make claims at a political level. The absence of this collectivization appears as a signal of the difficulties lone mothers encounter in gaining a kind of awareness of their collusion with the field or, otherwise, their preference for acts of resistance that aim to change the field from within (Pitzalis 2019; Casey 2021).

Analyzing the apex of the crisis—the separative path of the family in its contact with judicial institutions—also capacitates us to grasp the influence exerted by other fields on that same crisis, such as the practices and discourses that permeate the legal field with respect to the crisis of the family in the micro and macro social stances. The legal field, in a power relation with the family field, seems to mainly support the reproduction of practices concerning the orthodox definition of the family. They offer particular constructions of parenthood and parenting, emphasizing parents' specific characteristics and (in)capacities, sanctioning, or rewarding certain relations of authority or subordination within family relations.

This study is limited by size, and the application of Bourdieu's theory is limited to some aspects of the crisis in itself, rather than how mothers' trajectories and identity relations later change.

However, this analysis opens possibilities to expand studies on the family as a field and its ruptures and to apply Bourdieu's conceptual tools to study the crises of the contemporary family.

Particularly exciting is the matter of the exploration of children's power in the family field (Atkinson 2014, 228–9) during separations and how they can subvert rules and parents' domination. Furthermore, understanding how other fields work to support the reproduction of the family as a unit in the face of the crisis and to mend the tear of hysteresis and how they contend for orthodox and heterodox definitions of the family might be extremely useful to stimulate not only academics' but also policy makers' reflections.

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